

Technology and Microteaching: Exploring Teaching Behaviours and Preparing for a Tech-Driven Future

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This paper examined “Technology and Microteaching: Exploring Teaching Behaviours and Preparing for a Tech-Driven Future”. Quasi-experimental design was adopted. The study population was 319 NCE II students from Federal University of Education, Zaria. Sample of 60 students comprising of 30 in both experimental and control group. Two instruments were used for data collection, namely Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric (TBOR) and Preparedness for Tech-Driven Teaching Scale (PTDTS). The validity of the instruments was established by experts. A reliability coefficient of 0.72 was found for TBOR while 0.87 was found for PTDTS using Cronbach alpha. Descriptive statistics using means, standard deviations and t-test statistics were used to analyze the data collected. Result revealed that significant difference in teaching behaviours between pre-service teachers taught using technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods ($t = 8.7564, p < 0.05$). Participants in the technology-assisted microteaching demonstrated better teaching behaviours. Result also revealed that significant difference in pre-service teachers’ preparedness for tech-driven teaching between the two groups ($t = 10.2159, p < 0.05$). Those exposed to technology-assisted microteaching reported greater confidence in using digital tools, more effective lesson planning with technology. It was therefore recommended among others that: teacher education institutions should adopt technology-assisted microteaching as a core component of teacher training to strengthen pre-service teachers’ pedagogical skills and digital competence.

Keywords:
Technology,
Microteaching,
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Introduction

A teacher is someone that is trained and certificated to teach. He is regarded as the key player in the entire educational process, the mirror in the society and the father of knowledge. In performing his role of teaching, a teacher is expected to teach effectively. Effective teaching is an intelligent knowledge-based activity because it draws on a multiplicity of cognitive,

ffective and interpersonal element. There is therefore the need for quality training that can enhance effectiveness which can only be acquired through teacher education program. Proper practice is necessary for teacher training programmes. Teachers are not expected to have only the knowledge of subject matter but be well equipped with enough teaching skills. Ambili (2013)

posited that the prime quality of a teacher is effective teacher training.

In teaching and learning activities teachers and students begin to shift to the use of technology such as tabs and smartphones to support the achievement of learning goals. Teachers nowadays should be aware of the 4IR demands, hence the need to change their way of teaching in 21st century classrooms. The methods of teaching need to move towards Education 4.0, a term that emerges following the 4th Industrial Revolution. “Education 4.0 is a response to the needs of IR4.0 where human and technology are aligned to enable new possibilities” (Anealka, 2018). The most recent technology like artificial intelligence, robotics, and the Internet of Things (IoT) will replace some human jobs in the future, therefore it is crucial for the students today to possess skills that will not be replaceable by the technology. This is where the 21st century skills take place in today’s education. In order for students to be and stay relevant at the workplace, teachers and educators have to train them with the 21st century skills demanded in the 4IR. However, students would not be able to develop those skills if the teachers themselves have insufficient knowledge in training those skills to the students. Teachers do not only have to be subject matter experts, but they also need to know the pedagogy of teaching as emphasized by Shulman (1986) in his Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) framework. Meanwhile in the 21st century, it is essential for teachers to be well-versed in integrating technology into teaching. Therefore, they need to have knowledge on technology (Muhammad, Umar & Ahmadu, 2023).

More so, teaching in 21st century is no longer the same as before, as the priority of teaching has shifted. To ensure that students are able

to develop, practice and apply the 21st century skills, teachers need to be knowledgeable and competent in teaching and training the 21st century skills to the students. In general, when it comes to integrating technology in education, previous studies investigating teachers’ perspectives have shown that there are both positive and negative perspectives towards the integration of technology in the classroom. A study conducted by Ghavifekr and Wan (2015) revealed that most teachers are aware that ICT and digital technology are very useful in teaching, and these technologies help teachers to obtain more updated materials which improves their teaching skills. On top of that, Abu Bakar (2013) stated that the positive aspects of digital technology such as its attraction, convenience, multimodality, relevance, interactivity, and importance provide teachers with a lot of advantages in teaching. With these advantages that the digital technologies are providing, teachers are supposed to be able to integrate them successfully in the teaching and learning process.

However, many innovations are put up in teacher education for improvement. The innovation includes micro-teaching, simulated teaching, programmed instruction and computer assisted instruction. Unfortunately, microteaching that is supposed to be a training ground for the adequate teachers’ preparation is marred by poor educational policy, lack of equipment and instructional resources, ill-equipped staff and lack of infrastructural facilities. Microteaching serves as a meeting point between theory and practical for pre-service training of teachers. Micro-teaching, which is a sub-set of educational technology is an indispensable innovation in teacher education and preparation of student-teachers. It is when student-teachers acquire the necessary teaching skills through micro-teaching that they are

posted to the field for teaching practice. This explains why student-teachers are exposed to micro-learning/microteaching prior to teaching practice and in-service teaching for perfect training.

Microteaching was initially developed in Stanford University in early 1960's by Dwight Allen and his colleagues as an experimental programme with the aim of achieving excellence in teacher education (Wei, 2015).

Educators and scholars in the area of microteaching defined the term differently; microteaching serves as a meeting point between theory and practical for pre-service training of teachers. Microteaching, which is a sub-set of educational technology, is an indispensable innovation in teacher education and preparation of student-teachers. It is when student-teachers acquire the necessary teaching skills through microteaching that they are posted to the field for teaching practice (Oluwatoyin, 2020). Tata, Shehu and Aliyu (2015) viewed microteaching as assisting teacher trainees in acquiring teaching skills, confidence, reduction in anxiety and fear, proper class management, selection of teaching goals, preparation of lesson plan, ability to speak in front of group, selection of proper instructional materials as well as proper time management. Microteaching is organized practice teaching which is aimed at giving instructors confidence, support, and feedback by allowing them try out among friends and colleagues a short segment of what they plan to do with their pupils. It is considered one of the most effective tools in bridging the gap between theory and practice of teaching. It is a scaled down teaching encounter in terms of time, class size (number of students) and teaching complexity (Ike, 2017). In terms of time, microteaching is carried out between 5 to 10 minutes, in terms

of class size; 5-10 students are involved whereas one teaching skill is involved at a time.

According to Abendroth et al (2011), the basics of micro-teaching revolve around the six ideas as follows: (1) Plan: By asking the teachers to conduct a class for a small group of students, it gives teachers the bandwidth to plan appropriately. They plan the lesson and what they want to do in the class. Much like lesson planning but it won't be a full-fledged class. That is the first step in the micro-teaching cycle. The planning is done according to the instructions given by the trainer. (2) Teach: The next step is to teach. The trainee teaches the class according to the plan and conveys what they had prepared for. This will be supervised by the trainer. (3) Observe: The trainer observes the class that is conducted by the trainee teacher and comments and feedback are provided based on the observations made. (4) Re-plan: Based on the feedback provided by the trainer and reflection upon one's own performance, the teacher trainee re-plans their strategies and approach. This can be the presentation style, communication, or any necessary teaching skill. Creating a microteaching lesson plan is not an easy task. One should be mindful of all the aspects. (5) Re-teach: The same steps are repeated and the trainee teaches the class again. Microteaching is essentially a cyclic process and it heavily depends on the trial and error method. (6) Re-observe: Again, the teaching is observed and feedback is provided. As mentioned above, micro-teaching is a cyclic process. The trainees repeat and learn and hone their teaching skills so that they are prepared to face a class full of students with confidence.

The content of the teaching encounter is also reduced to a concept rather than a topic (Ike,

2017; Otsupius, 2014). In a nutshell, microteaching can be perceived as an important instructional means that mediates between educational theory and practice. Microteaching is a teacher education course designed to equip the would-be teachers with the teaching skills and competencies needed to perform as effective teachers in their chosen profession. The advantages of microteaching are numerous. It has the advantage of allowing the pre-service teachers to practice specific teaching strategies in a supportive, non-threatening laboratory environment. It also enables them to receive immediate detailed feedback to reinforce their didactic skills (Onwuagboke, Osuala & Nzeako, 2017).

However, one thing that adds glamour to and makes the evaluation process more objective, highly reflective, realistic and more practical is the integration of technology into microteaching (Ekpo-Eloma, Arikpo & Ebuta, 2013). For instance, with the aid of a video technology, all the instructional activities/actions during the microteaching sessions are captured, highlighted and later displayed and replayed for observation, comments and criticisms by both the supervising teacher, the student and colleagues. It further aids the teacher-trainee to sit back, watch and assess his strengths and weaknesses. Ekpo-Eloma et al., further asserted that incorporating video technology in microteaching session would heighten participants' interest and afford them ample opportunity to assess their performance exactly as it is without a modicum of doubt.

Research on application of technology in microteaching learning environment have been quite few. Some researchers have made attempts to find the effects of aspects of microteaching programmes on teaching effectiveness. For example, Oscar, (2012) examined video tape recorder (VTR) as a tool for the promotion of

effective teaching and learning in schools. The result of the investigation revealed that video-tape recorder is a powerful tool that promotes effective teaching and learning in schools. Similarly, Shanu (2016) investigated the impact of microteaching video feedback on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice. Findings of the investigation reveal that student teachers who were exposed to microteaching video feedback performed better in teaching practice than those that were not exposed to it. In a related study, Umeh, Mogbo and Nsofor, (2015) studied the effectiveness of VTR on micro-teaching on student teachers practice of stimulus variation skills. The findings of the study revealed that the use of video tape recorder effectively increased the performance of the pre-service teachers who were in the experimental group.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, technology has increasingly shaped the methods and strategies employed in teacher education, redefining how lessons are planned, delivered, and evaluated. Microteaching, as a widely used training approach for developing teaching competence among pre-service teachers, offers a controlled environment to practice and refine teaching behaviours such as questioning, explanation, feedback, and classroom management. However, in many Nigerian teacher education institutions, the integration of technology into microteaching remains limited, inconsistent, or poorly aligned with pedagogical goals. This creates a gap between the skills pre-service teachers develop during training and the demands of modern classrooms, where technology is rapidly becoming an indispensable tool for instruction and learner engagement. The extent to which technology integration influences teaching behaviours during

microteaching sessions remains underexplored, particularly in the Nigerian context.

Moreover, the global shift towards a technology-driven educational landscape fueled by advancements in digital tools, online learning platforms, and artificial intelligence demands that pre-service teachers be adequately prepared to teach in technology-rich environments. Without deliberate technology-assisted microteaching experiences, pre-service teachers may graduate with strong theoretical knowledge but inadequate confidence and competence to effectively integrate technology into real classroom settings. This raises concerns about their readiness to navigate the expectations of the 21st-century school system. There is, therefore, a pressing need to investigate not only how technology integration affects teaching behaviours during microteaching but also how such integration shapes pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven future.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives guided this study:

- To examine the influence of technology integration on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions.
- To assess the effect of technology-assisted microteaching on pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment.

Hypotheses

The following objectives were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho1: Technology integration has no significant effect on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions.

- Ho2: Technology-assisted microteaching does not significantly improve pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment.

Methodology

Quasi experimental design was adopted. It consisted of experimental group (treatment = technology integration) and control group (exposed to standard microteaching). The population of this study was 319 NCE II students from Federal University of Education, Zaria. The sample size for this study was 60 students comprising 30 in experimental group and 30 in control group, the sample drawn was line with central limit theorem which recommended 30 sample size for an experimental research. To categorize the students into experimental and control groups, simple random sampling technique in form of balloting was used. The names of the two groups was written in a paper and was tagged as experimental or control, folded and put into a container. Two students were asked to pick up the papers.

Two instruments were used for data collection. These were Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric (for microteaching) that comprises of aspects such as classroom organization, questioning & interaction, use of instructional strategies, time management, feedback & assessment, use of visuals/technology. It comprised of 18 items rated on 4-point Likert scale. The other instrument was Preparedness for Tech-Driven Teaching Scale that covered aspects of confidence using digital tools, lesson planning with technology, classroom management with tech, ability to evaluate edtech. It comprised of 12 items rated on 5-point Likert scale.

The validity and reliability of the instruments were established by experts. The reliability coefficient of the instruments were determining using Cronbach alpha statistical tool. A reliability coefficient of 0.72 was found for Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric while 0.87 was found for Preparedness for Tech-Driven Teaching Scale. Descriptive

statistics using means, standard deviations and independent t-test statistics were used to analyzed the data collected.

Results

Ho1: Technology integration has no significant effect on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions.

Table 1: Difference in teaching behaviours between pre-service teachers exposed to technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods.

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t-cal	p	Decision
Technology-Assisted Microteaching	30	62.8	5.2147	58	8.7564	0.000	Significant
Traditional Microteaching	30	54.1	4.9732				

Significant at $p < 0.05$, t -critical = 2.001

T-test analysis in Table 1 revealed a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance set for hypothesis testing. The calculated t-value (t-cal = 8.7564) was greater than the critical t-value (t-critical = 2.0017). This indicates a significant difference in teaching behaviours between pre-service teachers taught using technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods. Participants in the technology-assisted microteaching group scored higher on the Teaching Behaviour Observation Rubric, demonstrating stronger

skills in classroom organization, questioning and interaction, instructional strategies, time management, feedback and assessment, and use of visuals/technology. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that technology integration has no significant effect on teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions is rejected.

Ho2: Technology-assisted microteaching does not significantly improve pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment.

Table 2: Difference in preparedness for tech-driven teaching between pre-service teachers exposed to technology-assisted microteaching and those taught using traditional methods.

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t-cal	p	Decision
Technology-Assisted Microteaching	30	47.6	3.8254	58	10.2159	0.000	Significant
Traditional Microteaching	30	39.8	4.1372				

Significant at $p < 0.05$, t -critical = 2.0017

T-test analysis in Table 2 revealed a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 threshold. The calculated t-value ($t_{\text{cal}} = 10.2159$) exceeded the critical t-value ($t_{\text{critical}} = 2.0017$), indicating a significant difference in pre-service teachers' preparedness for tech-driven teaching between the two groups. Those exposed to technology-assisted microteaching reported greater confidence in using digital tools, more effective lesson planning with technology, stronger classroom management using technology, and higher ability to evaluate educational technology. Consequently, the null hypothesis which states that technology-assisted microteaching does not significantly improve pre-service teachers' preparedness for a tech-driven educational environment is rejected.

Discussion

Findings from this study revealed that technology integration significantly improved teaching behaviours during microteaching sessions. Pre-service teachers in the technology-assisted microteaching group demonstrated better organization, interaction, feedback provision, and use of instructional technology than those in the traditional group. This finding aligns with that of Shanu (2016) who investigated the impact of microteaching video feedback on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice. Findings of the investigation reveal that student teachers who were exposed to microteaching video feedback performed better in teaching practice than those that were not exposed to it. In a related study, Umeh, Mogbo and Nsofor, (2015) studied the effectiveness of VTR on micro-teaching on student teachers practice of stimulus variation skills. The findings of the study revealed that the use of video tape recorder effectively increased the

performance of the pre-service teachers who were in the experimental group. Similarly, Oscar, (2012) examined video tape recorder (VTR) as a tool for the promotion of effective teaching and learning in schools. The result of the investigation revealed that video-tape recorder is a powerful tool that promotes effective teaching and learning in schools.

Additionally, the study revealed that technology-assisted microteaching significantly improved pre-service teachers' preparedness for tech-driven teaching. Participants in the experimental group displayed higher levels of confidence and competence in integrating digital tools into lesson delivery. This result supports the findings of Ekpo-Eloma, Arikpo and Ebuta (2013) who asserted that with the aid of a video technology, all the instructional activities/actions during the microteaching sessions are captured, highlighted and later displayed and replayed for observation, comments and criticisms by both the supervising teacher, the student and colleagues. Incorporating technology in microteaching aids the teacher-trainee to sit back, watch and assess his strengths and weaknesses, it also heighten participants' interest and afford them ample opportunity to assess their performance exactly as it is without a modicum of doubt.

Conclusion

The results indicate that technology-assisted microteaching significantly enhances both teaching behaviours and preparedness for tech-driven teaching among pre-service teachers compared to traditional microteaching methods. Participants exposed to technology integration demonstrated superior classroom management, instructional strategies, use of technology, and confidence in applying digital tools in teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was recommended that:

Teacher education institutions should adopt technology-assisted microteaching as a core component of teacher training to strengthen pre-service teachers' pedagogical skills and digital competence.

Continuous professional development programmes should be organized for teacher educators to effectively design, implement, and assess technology-driven microteaching sessions.

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